

8th European Congress of Health Sciences

May 3-4, 2025 - Bristow, VA / USA (ONLINE)

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Official statement (April 6, 2024):

The official congress committee of the European Congress of Health Sciences (ECHS) consists of medical doctors working independently, and Aydan Çevik Varol MD, Assist. Prof. of Family Medicine working as a state university staff at Namik Kemal University, Faculty of Medicine, Department of Family Medicine, Tekirdag, Turkiye. This statement is placed here to declare that ECHS meets the UAK associate professorship application criteria in Turkey.

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Oral Presentations

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Oral Presentation-1

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.15057061

Terapia Regenerativa para Lesões Articulares: Avanços na Osteoartrite e Traumatismos

(Regenerative Therapy for Joint Injuries: Advances in Osteoarthritis and Trauma)

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RESUMO (POR)

INTRODUÇÃO: As lesões articulares, como a osteoartrite e os traumatismos, afetam milhões de pessoas e comprometem a mobilidade e a qualidade de vida. Como a cartilagem tem uma capacidade de regeneração limitada, encontrar soluções eficazes para tratar esses danos é um grande desafio. Nesse cenário, a terapia regenerativa surge como uma esperança, explorando novas abordagens para reparar e restaurar tecidos danificados.

OBJETIVO: O objetivo deste estudo é compreender como as terapias regenerativas estão avançando no tratamento das lesões articulares, analisando técnicas inovadoras como o uso de células-tronco, plasma rico em plaquetas (PRP) e biomateriais que estimulam a regeneração do tecido cartilaginoso.

METODOLOGIA: A pesquisa foi baseada em uma revisão da literatura científica, reunindo informações de artigos publicados nos últimos dez anos em bases de dados renomadas, como PubMed, Scielo e ScienceDirect. Foram considerados estudos clínicos e experimentais que avaliam a eficácia dessas terapias.

RESULTADOS E DISCUSSÃO: Os resultados indicam que essas abordagens têm demonstrado benefícios, reduzindo dor, melhorando a mobilidade e estimulando a regeneração da cartilagem. No entanto, os efeitos variam dependendo do estágio da lesão e da técnica utilizada.

CONCLUSÃO: Conclui-se que a terapia regenerativa representa um avanço promissor, trazendo novas possibilidades para pacientes com lesões articulares. Ainda assim, mais estudos são necessários para garantir a segurança, padronizar protocolos e ampliar sua aplicação na prática médica.

PALAVRAS-CHAVE: Regeneração Celular; Células Tronco; Terapia Biológica

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Oral Presentation-1 (*continue*)

ABSTRACT (ENG)

INTRODUCTION: Joint injuries, such as osteoarthritis and trauma, affect millions of people and compromise mobility and quality of life. Since cartilage has a limited regeneration capacity, finding effective solutions to treat this damage is a major challenge. In this scenario, regenerative therapy emerges as a hope, exploring new approaches to repair and restore damaged tissues.

OBJECTIVE: The objective of this study is to understand how regenerative therapies are advancing in the treatment of joint injuries, analyzing innovative techniques such as the use of stem cells, platelet-rich plasma (PRP) and biomaterials that stimulate the regeneration of cartilage tissue.

METHODOLOGY: The research was based on a review of the scientific literature, gathering information from articles published in the last ten years in renowned databases, such as PubMed, Scielo and ScienceDirect. Clinical and experimental studies that evaluate the effectiveness of these therapies were considered.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION: The results indicate that these approaches have shown benefits, reducing pain, improving mobility and stimulating cartilage regeneration. However, the effects vary depending on the stage of the injury and the technique used.

CONCLUSION: It is concluded that regenerative therapy represents a promising advance, bringing new possibilities for patients with joint injuries. Still, more studies are needed to ensure safety, standardize protocols and expand its application in medical practice.

KEYWORDS: Cellular Regeneration; Stem Cells; Biological Therapy.